

Digital Marketing Makes Consumer Closer: An Internet Giant Creating Challenges at Present:

A Study on Consumer Perspective During COVID-19

Ismat Ara Eti & Md. Murshedul Bari

Abstract:

All businesses approved many tactics where digital marketing is the unsurpassed one that is so flexible, trackable, and accessible and having exclusively placed to reach business ambitions. During the COVID-19 pandemic, incredible challenges faced by many businesses. Consumer awareness and attitude are imperative because it provides a good perception to create content about product or services. So here, digital marketing is light of heaven that has opened up the way to touch consumers. This paper has intentions to illustrate a wide present literature and on what is happening in the business world related to the idea of digital marketing and descriptive analysis is used to examine the practice during COVID-19 pandemic towards business performance. This paper mainly focus on conceptual understanding of digital marketing and is concerned with consumers and also allows the customers to interact with the product by virtue of digital media. The paper is based on secondary data such as many articles, reports, various websites and information on the internet have been reviewed. In this study, We agreed that businesses can genuinely benefit from Digital Marketing such as search engine optimization (SEO), content marketing, social media marketing, e-mail marketing, online advertising. It has converted one of the powerful weapons that make new alignment for all business so firms should plan an aimed attitude formulating planned conclusions.

**IJSB
Literature Review**

Accepted 09 September 2020
Published 15 September 2020
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4032466

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Digital Transformation, AIDA Model, Traditional vs Digital, Strategies, COVID-19: Impact on Ecommerce.

About Author (s)

Ismat Ara Eti (corresponding author), Independent University, Bangladesh.
Md. Murshedul Bari, Daffodil International University, Bangladesh.

Introduction

The main purpose of this paper is to distinguish the performance of digital advertising in the online competitive market and its contribution during the COVID-19 epidemic. The supporting objectives of this paper are to introduce the concept of digital marketing, digital transformation, the distinction between traditional advertising and digital marketing, various steps to build a successful digital business during the epidemic, digital marketing strategies. By using new techniques, marketers can target the market from technology that brings a new dimension to old-school marketing and transformation called digital marketing (Jain and Yadav, 2017, p. 49). Having separate both digital and offline sites is often essential to different digital business plans (Chaffey and Bosomworth, 2013, p. 3). Because of consumer demand based on products, services, prices from various providers, Internet development, World Wide Web and other digital technologies have changed (Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick, 2012). Electronic trading means any online market size that supports sales, purchasing, trading of products or services beyond. Google.com, Yahoo.com, Amazon.com, Alibaba.com and YouTube.com have been redesigned online (Read & Verma, 2018, page 323). According to tradition, offline and online users forced by government restrictions, deliberate self-disclosure on social media has also increased during the epidemic (Brough and Martin, 2020). Thanks to COVID-19, 63% of advertisers plan to change their messaging strategies and another 17% are still uncertain (LaBeau, 2020). According to a new study by NewsCred Insights (2020) launched during the epidemic, many companies used to predict and managing control projects across all marketing platforms, both internal and external consumers. Another new study by Nelms (2020) suggests that a consumer product or service can help companies switch to a digital workplace to expand the resilience strategies within COVID-19 where the business must reimburse customers for constant care in times of crisis and crisis.

Concept of Digital Marketing

As part of a digital marketing strategy aimed at informing the customer that develops communication strategies to increase customer attention in relation to the company and its products, to help attract buy-in options and make him or her loyal to the company's product. In addition, digital marketing mainly involves building trust and loyalty relationships with the customer and inbound marketing becomes a key component of digital marketing (Loredana, 2016, p. 62). There is another name for digital marketing online marketing. Recent research shows that online marketing is the process of performing online marketing activities and its tools are online products, price, location and promotions (Hossain & Rahman, 2017, p. 2). According to a recent study by Longo (2017) it has defined an effective digital marketing system based on customer-based strategies and establishing authority lines and providing key accountability frameworks that help reduce conflict and ensure efficient resource allocation. Some research suggests that Digital Marketing is referred to as achieving marketing objectives using digital technology that can help achieve marketing goals and has an external and internal perspective that includes managing internal and external digital communications (Chaffey, 2014, p. 5). Author Desai (2019, p. 196) makes a variety of digital marketing initiatives including all electronic or online marketing efforts with digital channels such as search engines, social media, email and their websites to communicate with current and potential customers can also be called 'online marketing'. 'online marketing' or 'web marketing'. According to Ryan's new idea (2014, p. 23), to understand digital marketing and transformation, firms can use only two keys to help determine whether a business needs a digital marketing strategy as an online audience or not, product / service firms / products are

suitable for the digital market or not. Digital marketing has a major impact on the business world between COVID-19. A study by Hootsuite & We Are Social (2020) shows e-commerce activity from any highly visible device thanks to COVID-19.

Figure 1 ECOMMERCE ACTIVITY OVERVIEW
by Hootsuite & We Are Social (2020)

Digital Transformation

According to the new research of FiNTECH (2017), e.com (2019), McRac, H. (2015), shows that Facebook, Airbnb, Uber and overwhelming growth of the contents creators has no own property, own cars are given in the below figure.

Table 1 Digital Transformation- Digitalization

Digital Transformation- Digitalization	
The world’s largest Taxi Company owns no vehicles - UBER	
The world’s most popular media owner creates no content - Facebook	
The world’s most valuable retailer, with no inventory - amazon, Alibab.com	
The world’s largest accommodation provider owns no real estate - Airbnb	
The world’s best-known streaming platform grew without content- Netflix	
The world’s largest advertising company does not produce its ads. - Google	
The world’s most effective advertising provider owns no billboards- Mobius	
The world’s most widespread video-sharing website has no own content- YouTube	
The world’s most popular photo-sharing platform, selling no camera - Instagram	

Source: FiNTECH (2017), e.com (2019), McRac, H. (2015)

COVID-19: Impact on Ecommerce Transactions

In research of Hootsuite & We Are Social (2020) shows e-commerce transactions have increased every category like sports equipment brands and supermarkets seeing particularly strong gains compared to pre-Coronavirus levels. But tourism transactions continue to be badly affected because of safety fears and ongoing travel restrictions.

Figure 2 COVID-19: IMPACT ON ECOMMERCE TRANSACTIONS by Hootsuite & We Are Social (2020)

Traditional marketing vs digital marketing

According to the new research of Das and Lall (2016), Bailey (2020) and Bhayani & Vachhani (2014) shows some major difference between traditional marketing and digital marketing.

Table 2: Traditional marketing vs Digital marketing

Area	Traditional Marketing	Digital Marketing
Focus Audience	Simpler to an extent with local consumers.	Touch the aimed audience globally from all over the world.
Marketing Tactic	Having more a person-to-person connection to notify brand.	The physical attendance of the marketers is not at all mandatory.
Documentation	Delivering the hard copy of products, services description	Delivering the description in softcopy over the internet.
Consumer Interface	Very less interaction is involved	More interaction in digital marketing through a digital platform.
Marketing Budget	Involved printing, radio, TV ads which create more cost	Less costly because all is online.
Communication	Involving one-way communication	Involving two-way communication
Product and service price	Negotiated with each customer	Set by the seller for all customers

Six Key Steps to Build a Successful Digital Business

According to the new research of McGee, Morello, & Weldon (2014) shows that digital business is the construction of innovative business designs that prerequisite six steps to building a successful digital business. At first the firms create the right mindset and distributed thoughtfully among important decision creators. In second step, the businesses put the right leaders in place to form the essential leadership team that will drive the compulsory revolution. Then, launch a digital business center of excellence to measure business skills and retort to opportunities and threats. According to the third step, the firms must formulate a digital business strategy in stage four that will provide a strategy to opportunities and threats guidance and develop the other essential elements of a digital strategy like product or service portfolio, technology, content, media etc. Business should find, develop or acquire the necessary knowledge, competencies and skills to execute on the digital business strategy. At last firms will creating new digital business capabilities with the firms' core knowledge, proficiencies and expertise essential for digital business achievement.

Figure 3 *Six Key Steps to Build a Successful Digital Business*
Photo sourced by SlideTeam (2020)

Digital Marketing with AIDA Model

Digital marketing theory can be shown in the AIDA model. Author Hadiyati (2016) presents that the AIDA model refers to Attention, Interest, Desire and Action. Recent research of Digital Adoption Team (2020) design virtual sales model with AIDA formula in digital strategy during COVID-19. In research from Schwarzl and Grabowska (2015, p. 194) & Hanlon (2019) describe the AIDA model theory. At the first stage, digital platforms draw the attention of the potential buyer. Then the ascribable in the search engines and creating interest in the benefits of product or service features inspired interest. Then next what makes product or services desirable through an emotional link with the positive responses and set the buying desire. At final, the search engine advert that moving the buyer to cooperate the following page brought the probable buyer to the action of purchase and so forth.

Figure 4 AIDA Model by Business-to-you (2019)

How has COVID-19 affected shopping?

Recent research of Rigby (2020) shows “More than three-quarters (78%) said they were shopping online for groceries to the same extent as previously following the outbreak, 14% are doing more of their grocery shopping online, 3.8% are shopping less, and 4% have stopped completely. Some 86% are buying electronics equipment online to the same extent, while 7% are buying more, 5% less, and 3% have stopped altogether. Most (83%) continue to buy clothes online at the same level as previously, while 10% are buying more, 5% buying less and 3% have stopped. Just under three-quarters (73%) are buying takeaway food to the same extent, 7% are buying more, 11% less and 7.5% have stopped.”

Figure 5 How Has COVID-19 (coronavirus) affected your shopping?
By Rigby (2020),

How Covid-19 impacts digital marketing background

The Financial Express (2020) shows due to COVID-19, all activities of a business are going online and emphasizing on website design and development to run the business. The study of Kim (2020) finds that the dominant two motivations for shopping in physical stores instead of shopping online are immediate possessions and social interactions, with more convenient and economical. Digital marketing reduces the distance between firms and their employees. The study of Kim (2020) finds at least 316 million people in 42 states have been asked to stay at home to slow down the pandemic. In this aspect, businesses have been susceptible to make substantial transformations. Researcher Mathradas (2020) shows that the outbreak may have already interrupted the supply chains of nearly 75 percent of all U.S. companies. Just as internal labor shortages could impact your operations, the same is true for your external

delivery systems, such as USPS, UPS, and FedEx. Recently, in United Nations conference on trade and development, UNCTAD (2020) presents in the spread of the new coronavirus is a serious risk to the macro economy through the halt in production activities, and cut-off of supply chains. The Financial Express (2020) shows some businesses are seriously stopped due to COVID-19 like restaurants, boutiques, salons for insufficient clients.

Digital Marketing Strategies

A) Online advertising: According to new research of shows (Yasmin, Tasneem & Fatema,2015, p.72) online advertising is a dynamic part of digital marketing, which has an additional name called internet advertising. Further researcher, Das (2016, p.8) says that online advertising can be done by procuring banner zone on a specific website. Therefore, the advertiser would pay to the website owner. Shadowing this concept another author sketchily explains the image of online advertising is accessible on the internet via numerous platforms include emails, websites, blogs and social channels (Gibson, 2018, p.14). During COVID-19 pandemic, online advertising plays vital rules where by staying at home people can easily get products/services through online advertising. Again, researcher shows the monthly shopping activity from January to June 2020 with page views rate and orders counts rate (Hottenroth, V. 2020).

Figure 6 Monthly Shopping Activity, Global 2020, from Bazaarvoice Blog by Veronica Hottenroth (2020)

B) Email Marketing: Original research of Zakowicz (2020) bestows that email is an effectual communication tool and COVID-19 have a remarkable effect on email marketing as a calculation, consumers moved to brand emails. Bestowing to new research (Yasmin, Tasneem & Fatema,2015, p.72) shows that email marketing is the best option because of low-cost advertising and building brand and brand awareness, customer loyalty and trust. Another author finds this strategy permits a firm to capture an enormous customer by exercising an electronic messaging instrument as an illustration of distributing of coupons, online newsletters, promotional events and advertising materials (Gibson,2018, p.13). Gadimova (2020) highlighted business should estimate for appositeness, implementation and subdivision strategies and study some issues before sending an email like avoid Covid-19

oversoaked information. Another writer shows the email open rates during COVID-19 compared with 2019 to 2020 from January to April are higher than 2019 given below.

Figure 7 Email open rates by Zakowicz, G. (2020)

C) Social Media Marketing: According to new research (Yasmin, Tasneem & Fatema,2015, p.73) shows that social media sanctions people to build, share ideas, information and images about the company’s product or services. Yogesh & Sharaha, (2019) shows, it is the effective marketing of media advertising having fixed or animated images, which take place on various websites for promoting brands (p.13). Another author exposed some websites such as Google+, Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, and YouTube, Instagram where social media marketing having popularity (Das, 2016, p.8). During COVID-19, social media is being the best option for business to reach consumers at a low budget. According to the new research of Kemp, S. (2020) shows the advertising audience on various social media where the highest number of people can be reached with advertise. Table 03 showed the number that can be reached with advertise during the pandemic.

Table 3: Advertising Audience Overview

Advertising Audience Overview	Number of People can be Reached with Adverts on Social Media
Facebook	2.09 billion
Instagram	1.08 billion
LinkedIn	702 million
Twitter	326 million
Pinterest	179 million

Source: Digital 2020, July Global Statshot by Simon Kemp (2020)

D) Text Messaging: According to new research (Yasmin, Tasneem & Fatema,2015, p.73), It is a way to send information about the products and services from cellular and smartphone devices. Business can send information in the form of text or Short Message Service SMS, pictures, video or audio or MMS. In Europe and Asia, marketing through cellphone SMS befitted progressively popular in the early 2000s.

E) Affiliate Marketing: New researcher reveals that as a trust-worthy strategy to generate income online for any type of business (Gibson, 2018, p.14). The economic power can be spotted at the time of Covid-19 and affiliate marketers punch their positions for effectiveness (Dar, 2020) and dealing with low commission rates (Singson,2020). According to new research (Yasmin, Tasneem & Fatema, 2015, p.73), affiliate marketing is performance-oriented marketing where a company pays affiliates for each visitor. Author Das (2016, p.9) exposed four main participants in affiliate marketing such as the merchant, the network, the publisher and the customer.

F) Search Engine Optimization (SEO): Bestowing to the new research (Yasmin, Tasneem & Fatema,2015, p.73) shows that search engine optimization defines the process of affecting a website or a web page in a search engine's natural or maybe un-paid organic mode. As a smart and unique investment, it has cost-effective benefits (Baker,2020). According to him other author shows some benefits of SEO during COVID-19 such as cost-effective, long-term growth, generate trust, search by small keywords (Nizam,2020). Another researcher pointed out that 88% of the worldwide access of the web attempts done the Google search engine (Gibson,2018, p.13). According to the writer, Kaushal (2020) shows due to COVID-19, the search trends have some negative impact where yoga & personal trainers, amusement park, tour and travel websites are decreased 51%, 44%, 46% respectively.

G) Mobile Marketing: Mobile advertising is a type of advertising via wireless phones or other mobile devices such as smartphones, or tablet computers. It may take by rich media display ads, Short Message Service (SMS) or Multimedia Messaging Service (MMS) ads, mobile search ads, advertising within mobile websites, or ads within mobile applications or games (Das, 2016, p.8). It is a part of the software that need to be download from internet or mobile apps (Ryan, 2014b, p.209). According to the new research of WARC (2020), coronavirus has shifted consumer behavior towards mobile and another research shows that 68% of grocery shoppers are now operating groceries shop mobile apps (BizReport, 2020).

H) Digital Public Relations: For better responses, farms need to employ influencer to carry the brand message with the core value that will forward to target audience in a planning manner that is called digital public relations (Ryan, 2014b, p.266). This improbable approach is used to distribute company information, names of management officials, product information, investor information, organization history and a variety of extra information (Gibson,2018, p.14). Newsletters, feature articles, press conferences, authoritative views of those deliveries' exhibitions and fairs, event marketing are the segment of this (Eti and Bari, 2020, p.15). During COVID-19 pandemic, public profile agent turn into digital agent to delivery brand awareness, information vai social media live and by delivering the value of brand, many public relations professionals feeling self-confident along with more breakdown because of the pandemic (Nanji, 2020).

I) Content Marketing: Content marketing is a very influential brand-building instrument where a content marketer's skill to summary data and look at trends associations with imagination to express an overall content strategy. (Ryan, 2014b, p.308). Once a communication circle is created it is easier to deliver the information because their responsiveness is already received (Content Marketing Institute 2017). The expressions of delivered online articles, exhibitions, live streaming, pictures and videos as advantageous tools that companies should embrace into their blogs and the business website (Gibson,2018,

p.14). Author Keshari (2020) shows that for COVID-19, virtual gathering created by content marketing like ZOOM. Content marketing allows brands to become storytellers and provide important information especially during times of crisis (Fukano, 2020).

J) Inbound Marketing: “Inbound marketing is the strategy of connecting with potential customers through materials and experiences they find useful. Using media like blogs and social networking, marketers hope to entertain and inform viewers with content they seek by themselves” (Marketing-Schools.org, 2012). This strategy emphasizes on creating meaningful content to attract prospective customers by using different approaches (Assiriyage, et, al.,2018, p. 14). As a holistic approach it also combines other online marketing techniques like search engine optimization, social media marketing, e-mail marketing, etc (Bezovski, 2015).

Limitations of the study

Based on this study, it can further be extended to compare the digital marketing techniques with specific and the effectiveness of digital marketing with respect to different business can be analyzed.

Conclusion

Digital marketing proposals a titan amount of potentials for businesses. During COVID-19, it is far simpler for customers to discovery alternates from competitors on the internet. The ambition of this research paper was to inspect the finest digital marketing schemes, through a thorough and its presentation during COVID-19. This present study exposed numerous digital marketing tactics that are convenient to companies, businesses, non-profits, educational services and other professional zones. This paper meaningfully clears the difference between traditional marketing and digital marketing. The body of research jagged the practice of the internet in digital marketing as being a strategic resource in digital marketing. The internet is a principal spot that companies’ procedure to market products and services and noted the cost-to-benefit. Developing a website, apps and using the internet acts as a platform to a superfluity of strategies notorious in the theory. These strategies include SEO, E-mail Marketing, Online Ads, Digital Public Relations, Affiliate Marketing and Content Marketing. After a broad analysis, it can easily claim digital marketing is the good option for all business to adapt modernization and adjust all situation for reaching to consumers.

Declaration of Conflicting Interest

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research authorship and publication of the research.

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Cite this article:

Ismat Ara Eti & Md. Murshedul Bari (2020). Digital Marketing Makes Consumer Closer: An Internet Giant Creating Challenges At Present, A Study On Consumer Perspective During COVID-19. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 4(10), 64-76. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4032466>

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